
TYPES OF DICTIONARIES: STANDARDS, NORMS AND PROBLEMS OF COMPLYING TERMINOLOGICAL DICTIONARIES

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Abstract : This article provides feedback on the concept of a dictionary, dictionaries a dictionary it's types, description and classification.

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A dictionary is a linguistic product that brings together a chosen set of words or other language units and provides information about them. The way the entries are selected and ordered in a dictionary constitutes its macrostructure and the information about the entries, its microstructure.

Dictionaries vary both according to the linguistic information they contain and the purpose they serve. Typologies of dictionaries are usually based on the deviation of the various types of dictionaries with respect to the basic lexicographic pattern established by general language dictionaries. There are many types of dictionary: children's dictionaries, illustrated dictionaries, terminological dictionaries, translation dictionaries, learning dictionaries, biographical dictionaries, quotation dictionaries, retrograde dictionaries, dictionaries of slang, curses and dialects, dictionaries of proper names and dictionaries of synonyms, rhyming dictionaries and technical dictionaries, electronic dictionaries and online dictionaries. In short, there are so many that it would be impossible to list them all here.

General dictionaries are usually classified according to the following criteria and contain the following information:

Sources for the information: a selection of various source materials, most of which are written

Choice of entries: the most usual forms

Form for entries: e.g. the lexeme

Order of entries: e.g. alphabetical

Information accompanying each entry: grammatical category, definition, semantic uses determined by the field of usage or by change of meaning processes, examples illustrating usage

Primary purpose: e.g. descriptive

Type of reader: e.g. reasonably educated speaker

Purpose of the dictionary: e.g. increasing the competence of the user or resolve linguistic vacillations or gaps.

Any dictionary that deviates from this pattern is a special dictionary because of any of the following variations of structure and content:

The sources: e.g. a dictionary of the languages used by one author

The choice of entries: e.g. a dictionary of physics; a basic dictionary, if the criterion for selection is the extension of a form; a dialect dictionary

The nature of entries: e.g. a dictionary of collocations or fixed expressions

The order of the entries and the arrangement of the information: e.g. a thesaurus

The type of specific supplementary information that systematically accompanies the entry: e.g. the origin and evolution of the word (etymological dictionaries), geographic varieties (dialect dictionaries)

The social function it aims at: e.g. a dictionary of standard usage

The target group: e.g. a school-age dictionary

The specific uses aimed at: e.g. a dictionary for editors and technical writers; a bilingual dictionary for translation.

The dictionary is not only used as a reference work, it also often serves as a kind of storage facility, a storeroom for a language in which we can find much of what once existed and what exists today.

Sidney Landau, a distinguished lexicographer, says that making dictionaries is not a theoretical exercise to increase the sum of human knowledge but practical work to put together text that people can understand. His classic volume *Dictionaries: The Art and Craft of Lexicography* is warmly recommended for anyone who wants to know what goes on in the production of a published dictionary. Johnson says that the value of a work must be estimated by its use.

Dictionaries are not born every day. They are hugely expensive to produce from scratch, and most new dictionaries still owe much to some earlier incarnation. For lexicographers the birth of a new dictionary offers exciting opportunities. The potential for improvement and innovation is almost infinite, but two general principles have to be kept in mind:

- Space is finite and has to be used intelligently;
- A dictionary is like an eco-system: decisions about content, presentation,
- And design can't be made in isolation, because a change to one part of the system impacts on all the other parts of it.

It is sometimes useful to think of the dictionary in database terms, as a set of components, such as definitions, etymologies, and pronunciations that can be dealt with discretely. But when planning a dictionary, we have to think of it as a complete system, in which all these components are inextricably related to one another. To give a concrete example: one of the decisions the editor of an English dictionary has to make at the planning stage is how to handle inflections. The options include:

- Showing full inflections for every word (thus sail, sails, sailing, sailed);
- Showing inflections only when they are irregular;
- Not showing them at all.

A dictionary is a systematically arranged list of socialized linguistic forms compiled from the speech-habits of a given speech community and commented on by the author in such a way that the qualified reader understands the meaning of each separate form, and is informed of the relevant facts concerning the function of that form in its community.

Compiling a dictionary involves making decisions at the planning stage and as the project goes forward smaller ones on a day-to-day basis. Many of these decisions entail some form of selection, because every dictionary contains a subset of all the available information about the target language and its vocabulary. For example, at any given point in the editorial process, you may have to decide whether to include a particular headword and, if so, how much information to give about it.

Dictionaries are not just used for professional purposes but also for sheer pleasure. For example, they can be used when playing language games. The formal properties of the electronic dictionary have greatly improved the support offered to this function of the dictionary, allowing incorporating for example a lexicon of anagrams and a reverse index of headwords.

The linguistic function of the terminological dictionary is mainly achieved on the microstructural level. The formal characteristics of the entry term itself is the first indicator of the linguistic nature of a term. Next within an entry come all kinds of labels, such as grammatical, syntactical, pragmatic, etymological, orthographic, register, etc., phonetic transcription, collocational patterns, usage example.

Compilation of modern terminological reference works, including terminological dictionaries, should be subjected to the primary goal of modern terminography, i.e. making terminological dictionaries that fulfil theoretical requirements, convey specialist knowledge in the most effective manner, and meet the needs of its users. These requirements will influence the elements of macro-, medio- and microstructure and will result in the compilation of various types of

terminographical works. Some users, for example terminologists or students, may require detailed concept description. For them, such elements of a dictionary structure as explicit representation of semantic relations between terms, classification schemes and precise definitions are of primary importance.

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